

2-Aminothiazole Derivatives. Part III

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Phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphides and sulphones, bearing halogeno and methoxy substituents in the benzenoid ring, have been synthesised with a view to studying their antibacterial activity. 2-Acetamido-5-bromothiazole has been condensed with equimolecular quantity of the potassium salt of various substituted thiophenols in presence of propylene glycol to furnish the corresponding phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl sulphides which have been oxidised to their respective sulphones by hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid. The acetamido-sulphides and -sulphones have been hydrolysed by EtOH-HCl to the required amino-sulphides and -sulphones.

The present communication is a continuation of the previous work¹ on 2-aminothiazole derivatives and describes the synthesis of the following phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphides and sulphones.

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| (i) $R=Cl$; $R^1=R^2=R^3=H$. | (v) $R=R^2=OMe$; $R^1=R^3=H$. |
| (ii) $R^1=Cl$; $R=R^2=R^3=H$. | (vi) $R^1=Cl$; $R^2=OMe$; $R=R^3=H$. |
| (iii) $R^2=Br$; $R=R^1=R^3=H$. | (vii) $R^1=R^2=Cl$; $R=R^3=H$. |
| (iv) $R=OMe$; $R^1=R^2=R^3=H$. | |

The method adopted for condensing 2-acetamido-5-bromothiazole with potassium salt of a thiophenol is essentially the same as that described in the previous paper¹, except for carrying out the reaction in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen with the object of increasing the yield of the condensation product. But there was no considerable improvement in the yield. The substituted phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl sulphides were converted into the corresponding sulphones on oxidation with either hydrogen peroxide or potassium permanganate² in acetic acid. These acetamido-sulphides and -sulphones were hydrolysed with ethanolic HCl to the respective amino-sulphides and -sulphones. The amino-sulphides formed monohydrochlorides on heating with ethanolic HCl and monopicrates on treating with a saturated solution of picric acid in ethanol. The amino-sulphones rarely formed these derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

The starting compounds like *o*-chloro-, *m*-chloro-, *p*-bromo-, *o*-methoxy-, and 2,5-dimethoxy-thiophenol were prepared from the corresponding anilines according to the

1. Mahajanshetti and Nargund, *this Journal*, 1963, 39, 427.
2. Hoggarth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 110.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

modified³ Leuckart reaction. 3-Chloro-4-methoxythiophenol and 3,4-dichlorothiophenol were prepared by reducing the benzenesulphonyl chlorides, obtained on chlorosulphonation of *o*-chloroanisole and *o*-dichlorobenzene respectively. 2-Acetamido-5-thiothiazole was prepared according to Backer and Buisman⁴.

Phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl Sulphides and Sulphones.—A mixture of 2-acetamido-5-bromothiazole (0.02*M*), potassium salt of a thiophenol (0.02*M*), and freshly distilled propylene glycol (15-20 ml) was heated at 130-40° for about 4 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice and the crude product was macerated with a 10% NaOH solution. It was filtered, washed with water, dried (P₂O₅), treated with boiling acetic anhydride (10 ml), and further worked up in the usual way. The sulphides were purified by crystallisation from acetic acid as colorless shining needles. To a solution of a sulphide (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid was added 30% H₂O (2 ml) and the mixture left for 48 hours with intermittent addition of the H₂O (0.5 ml) at intervals of 12 hours. The crystalline solid separating was purified by recrystallisation from acetic acid in colorless needles (Table I).

TABLE I

Phenyl-2-acetamido-5-thiazolyl sulphides and sulphones.

S. No.	R _X	Yield.	M.P.	% Nitrogen	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>o</i> -Chloro Sulphone	82% *	215-16° 225-26°	9.97	9.84
				8.61	8.95
2	<i>m</i> -Chloro Sulphone	80 *	162-63° 261-62°	9.68	9.84
				8.98	8.85
3	<i>p</i> -Bromo ⁵ Sulphone	77 *	204-205° 291-92°	8.69	8.51
				7.88	7.78
4	<i>o</i> -Methoxy Sulphone	78 *	196-97° 271-72°	10.05	10.00
				9.13	8.97
5	2,5-Dimethoxy Sulphone	80 *	169-70° 238-39°	9.11	9.08
				8.24	8.19
6	3-Chloro-4-methoxy Sulphone	78 *	237-38° 264-65°	8.84	8.90
				8.21	8.08
7	3,4-Dichloro Sulphone	79 *	200-201° 260-61°	8.62	8.78
				8.04	7.98

*65-75% yield.

3. Mahajanshetti et al., *J. Karnataka Univ.*, 1961, Sci. No. VI. 9.

4. *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1944, 63, 226.

5. Inoue et al., *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1951, 71, 551, report m.p. 206°.

TABLE II

Phenyl-amino-5-thiazolyl sulphides and their monohydrochlorides, monopictates, and sulphones.

S.No.	Rx.	Yield.	*Solvent.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.		
					Found.	Reqd.	
1	o-Chloro Hydrochloride	75%	A	168-69°	11.38	11.52	
		..	B	175-76°	10.12 (277)	10.03 (270)	
	Pictate Sulphone	..	B	219-20°	14.69	14.85	
		64	A	243-44°	10.40	10.20	
	2	m-Chloro Hydrochloride	72	A	139-40°	11.66	11.54
			..	D	166-69°	10.20 (284)	10.03 (270)
Pictate Sulphone		..	B	188-89°	14.04	14.85	
		65	B	196-97°	10.34	10.20	
3		p-Bromo Hydrochloride	65	A	175-76°	9.89	9.76
			..	B	226-27° (decomp.)	8.70 (320)	8.66 (324)
	Pictate Sulphone	..	B	222-23°	13.78	13.57	
		60	B	227-28°	8.99	8.78	
	4	o-Methoxy Hydrochloride	80	A	134-35°	11.69	11.77
			..	B	118-19°	10.31 (271)	10.20 (275)
Pictate Sulphone		..	B	196-97°	14.85	14.99	
		60	A	207-208°	10.40	10.37	
5		2,5-Dimethoxy Hydrochloride	75	C	147-48°	10.37	10.45
			..	B	170-72° (decomp.)	9.12 (309)	9.20 (305)
	Pictate Sulphone	..	B	200-201°	14.20	14.08	
		58	A	214-15°	9.19	9.33	
	6	3-Chloro-4-methoxy Hydrochloride	70	A	158-59°	10.24	10.28
			..	B	180-81°	9.14 (312)	9.06 (306)
Pictate Sulphone		..	B	210-11°	13.78	13.96	
		60	B	203-205°	9.26	9.20	
7		3,4-Dichloro Hydrochloride	80	A	128-29°	10.20	10.11
			..	B	155-56°	9.10 (310)	8.93 (314)
	Pictate Sulphone	..	B	222-23°	14.00	13.83	
		55	A	196-97°	9.21	9.06	

N.B. Figures in parentheses refer to equiv. weights.

* A=aqueous ethanol; B=ethanol; C=benzene-ligroin (60-80°).

Phenyl-2-amino-5-thiazolyl Sulphides and Sulphones.—A mixture of acetamide-sulphide or -sulphone (1 g.), ethanol (20-25 ml), and HCl (conc., 2 ml) was heated under reflux for about an hour. The solvents were removed *in vacuo* and the residue basified with dilute ammonia to obtain the corresponding amino-sulphide or -sulphone. The product was purified by crystallisation from a suitable solvent. Various amino-sulphides and their derivatives like hydrochlorides, picrates, and sulphones are described in Table II.

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